

A Note on the Equivalence Principle Applicability to the General Theory of Relativity

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Abstract

Here we are talking about the equivalence of Einsteinian gravitation equations solutions to relativist accelerated frames. It was established that there is a uniformly accelerated frame. Such a frame is deformed as an acceleration result, but it is a stiff frame according to Born, i.e. its metric tensor does not depend on time. The frame is pseudo-Riemannian. It was proved that a uniformly accelerated frame is locally equivalent to the relevant solution of Einstein's gravitational equation.

Keywords: The Equivalence Principle, Local Equivalence Principle, Relativity Principle, Einstein's Equation, The General Relativity Theory, Non-inertial frames, Pseudo-Riemann Geometry.

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1. Introduction

In [1], A. Einstein put forward the principle of equivalence as a research method of relativistic gravitation theory. The first step in this direction was an investigation of *evenly and uniformly accelerated frame*², which shall be equivalent to a stationary uniform gravitational field according to the equivalence principle. At the same time, a concrete form of such a frame remains unknown.

It would seem that according to the equivalence principle, a metric of uniformly accelerated frame shall coincide with a metric of uniform gravitational field obtained by Einstein's equation solution. However, V.A. Fock [2] showed that Moeller's accelerated frame [3] and an approximate solution of Einstein's gravitation equation are equivalent only locally and approximately. Fock concluded from this particular case that the equivalence principle is not an universal law. Literally: "*The comparison of two expressions for the squared interval, which we made, indicates that in the absence of gravity the reference frame in accelerated motion really represents a well-known analogy with inertial reference frame in the presence of gravity field.* However, this comparison also indicates that this analogy is far from complete, so **there can be no question of a complete equivalence or indistinguishability of acceleration and gravity fields**" (this fragment was marked out in bold type by V. Morozov). This position calls into question a legitimacy of classical approach to the equivalence principle, which is formulated as follows:

"At each point P all the nature laws, expressed through local Lorentz coordinates x^i , have the same form as in the special theory of relativity (STR)" (§ 9.7 [3]).

Fortunately, Fock's viewpoint was not widespread, but gave some support to attempts to develop theories, which are an alternative to the general theory of relativity. For example, the relativistic gravitation theory [4] comes from the contraposition of inertia and gravitation forces. Various aspects of the equivalence principle have been repeatedly discussed, including papers [2, 5-7]. Of course, Fock's viewpoint arose not from the theory misunderstanding, but because Moeller's

accelerated frame is not uniformly accelerated (see Annexes, p. 2). Thus, a metric comparison of inhomogeneously accelerated frame with a uniform gravitational field is incorrect. The problem resolution appears to be in the metric comparison, as Fock did, but in replacing the Moeller's frame metric with the metric of uniformly accelerated reference frame. Hereinafter, we will show that these metrics are at least locally equivalent.

2. Time in Accelerated Frames

An integral part of the relativity theory is the relativity of event simultaneity. It is important to note that standard clock readings depend on not only its speed, but also its position in space. In addition, Einstein [1] showed that the rate of clock at different points of accelerated frame is different even at zero speed of these points. This result was the first step on the path to the general relativity theory and it eliminates the famous Einsteinian apparent clock paradox [2, 3].

Considering of frames with one-dimensional motion along the axis x and zero relative velocity. Choosing two points A_0 and A_1 with coordinates $x_0 = 0$ and $x_1 = \xi_1 > 0$ in the accelerated reference frame N . Let S be an inertial reference frame, associated with the point A_0 . Comparison of pendulum frequencies of standard clock, placed in the point A_0 , will give the same result – ν_0 in both reference frames. If ν_1 is the frequency of standard clock at the point A_1 from the viewpoint of an observer in the frame S , then according to [1]

$$\nu_1 = \nu_0(1 + \alpha \xi_1/c^2), \quad (1)$$

where α is the acceleration of the frame.

Some time later, Einstein [8] gave a simple proof of relation (1). Let the points A_0 and A_1 have a zero speed at the instant time $t_0 = 0$ in the inertial frame S . If the light was emitted with the frequency ν_0 from the point A_0 at the instant time t_0 , then when achieving the point A_1 this point will have a velocity $\alpha \xi_1/c$ and, by virtue of Doppler principle, it will have a greater frequency ν_1 whence it follows the expression (1). This expression is locally faithful, i.e. faithful in the limit $\xi_1 \rightarrow 0$. Einstein [1] noted that in the expression (1) the possible small changes in the interval ξ_1 can be neglected. This means that the

² In such a frame, all points have a permanent and proper acceleration.

expression (1) is universal, since nothing is used but the relativity principle and Doppler effect in proving this expression at the velocities much less than a light velocity. It is observed that in the modern courses of general relativity theory a proof of relation (1) is usually presented in the same form [8].

2. Does the Body Shape Depend on Acceleration?³

Comparing a standard clock frequency in reverse order [9], i.e. sending a light signal from the point A_1 to the point A_0 , we will obtain another result

$$v_0 = v_1(1 - \alpha \xi_0/c^2), \quad (2)$$

where ξ_0 is the distance between the points A_1 and A_0 . We see that the expressions (1) and (2) do not coincide for $\xi_0 = \xi_1$. This means that **there are no uniformly accelerated frames, preserving the spatial scales**. This does not contradict the assertion that uniformly accelerated frames shall be stiff according to Born, i.e. spatial patterns (rulers) of such a frame do not depend on time (see Annexes, p. 1).

The expression (1) can be considered as a local relation between proper times of inertial frame S' and accelerated frame S in the vicinity of the origin.

$$(1 + \alpha x/c^2)d\tau' = d\tau. \quad (3)$$

Let the spatial interval be $d\sigma = \sqrt{dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2}$, then the law of accelerated motion of a point in the intrinsic reference frame is given by equalization

$$d\sigma = \frac{1}{2}\alpha d\tau^2.$$

Whence, taking into account the equality (3), it follows

$$(1 + \alpha \xi/c^2)^2 d\sigma' = d\sigma. \quad (4)$$

³ In the article [1] of 1907, A. Einstein formulated the question: "At first, let's consider a body, which separate material points at some certain instant time t in the unaccelerated reference frame S rest with respect to S , but have a certain acceleration. *How does this acceleration influence the body shape in the reference frame S ?*" This question has not been answered.

3. Metric of Uniformly Accelerated Frame. Local Equivalence of Uniformly Accelerated Frame to Einstein's Equation Solution

Substituting values of (3) and (4) into the metric of Minkowski space

$$ds'^2 = c^2 dt'^2 - d\sigma'^2,$$

we will obtain the metric of uniformly accelerated reference frame

$$ds^2 = (1 + \alpha x/c^2)^2 c^2 dt^2 - (1 + \alpha x/c^2)^{-2} d\sigma^2. \quad (5)$$

This metric is stiff from Born's viewpoint since its metric tensor is diagonal with coefficients not depending on time. Since the tensor's elements are accurate, this metric is only locally faithful in the limit $x \rightarrow 0$.

After the inertia field potential $-\alpha x$ replacing in the metric (5) with the gravitational field potential U , it is possible, following Fock, to compare (5) with an approximate (accurate in the limit $x \rightarrow 0$) solution of the Einstein's equations for uniform gravitational field [2]

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2U}{c^2}\right) (cdt)^2 - \left(1 + \frac{2U}{c^2}\right) d\sigma^2.$$

This metric coincides with the metric (5) in the limit $x \rightarrow 0$. Thus, the equivalence principle is locally faithful.

The relativity principle in homogeneous frames occurs naturally. In the small vicinity of any point of such a frame, a standard clock goes identically, formula (2). In the vicinity of the same point, scales look the same, formula (4).

4. Conclusions and Outlook

Initiated by Einstein in 1907 [1], a development direction of relativistic gravitation theory through the equivalence principle did not lead to a full solution of gravity problems, since we failed to associate a gravitational field with masses of gravitating bodies. Despite this, the equivalence principle allows to obtain physically meaningful results. Sommerfeld [10] gave Lenz's example allowing to obtain a length element, which is coincident with Schwarzschild's solution. Of course, such logical constructions can not compete with the general relativity theory, but they probably can considerably supplement it. Therefore, it is required to achieve in-depth understanding of relativistic effects in non-inertial

frames as an intermediate link between general principles of the relativity theory and the gravitation theory.

Metric of uniformly accelerated frame (5) is pseudo-Riemannian. Riemannian tensor of this frame contains 24 non-zero terms, and the scalar curvature

$$R = \frac{4\alpha}{c^2}.$$

This convinces us once again that we live in the non-Euclidean world and provides a new look at the general relativity theory results.

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Annexes

A.1 Considering an accelerated frame. Let the law of motion of this frame points be

$$\alpha(\tau) = \begin{cases} \alpha, & 0 < \tau < T \\ 0, & \tau < 0 \text{ и } T < \tau, \end{cases} \quad (\text{I})$$

where τ is the proper time of the points. At the initial time the points have zero velocity in the inertial reference frame S. Let's select two points, the distance between which is equal to L in the frame S. Some finite time later, the points acquire the same speed v . Let's select the inertial reference frame S' , where the points speed is zero at the instant time T . Let's assume that the distance between these points equals L' in the frame S' . Let's ask ourselves, what is the coefficient χ equal to, which links these proper distances $L' = \chi L$? To do this, let's consider the frame with a motion

$$\alpha(\tau) = \begin{cases} -\alpha, & T < \tau < 2T \\ 0, & \tau < T \text{ и } 2T < \tau. \end{cases} \quad (\text{II})$$

According to the relativity and space homogeneity principle, the points acceleration shall also lead to the same result in this case, that is, it leads to the distance change between points in the intrinsic frame $L'' = \chi L'$. Sequential use of (I) and (II) results in $L'' = \chi L' = \chi^2 L$. On the other hand, for reversibility of motion in time it is required that the equality $L'' = L$ is valid, whence it follows that $\chi = 1$.

Thus, **the theorem is proved**. It follows from the principle of relativity and reversibility in time that in homogeneous and isotropic space the distance between the points in the intrinsic reference frame is permanent if the laws of their motion in the intrinsic reference frame are the same. In particular, the accelerated frame (5) is stiff in the sense that its metric tensor is independent of time. The theorem is a generalization of the trivial fact that a proper length of line segment in inertial frames is invariant.

The converse is not true. Giving an example of stiff accelerated frame, which is not uniformly accelerated.

A.2 Moeller's reference frame [3, 12] is obtained by transformation

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \left(1 + \frac{\alpha \tilde{x}}{c^2}\right) \frac{c^2}{\alpha} \cosh \frac{\alpha \tau}{c}, t \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{\alpha \tilde{x}}{c^2}\right) \frac{c}{\alpha} \sinh \frac{\alpha \tau}{c}, t \\ &= \tilde{t}, z = \tilde{z}. \end{aligned}$$

The frame is not uniformly accelerated. According to [3], an acceleration of points in the inertial frame

$$\gamma = \alpha \left(1 + \frac{\alpha \tilde{x}}{c^2}\right)^{-1}$$

and acceleration \mathbf{a} in the intrinsic reference frame in a vector notation [3]

$$\mathbf{a} = -\alpha \left(1 + \frac{\alpha \tilde{x}}{c^2}\right)$$

Thus, Moeller's frame is stiff, but not uniformly accelerated. However, the stiffness of such a frame can not be provided with the help of deformable bodies, since the force density, according to the last expression is non-uniform, and the body will be in a stress condition. Possibility of destruction imposes restrictions both on the accelerated body accelerations and dimensions.

A.3 It is fairly often claimed that the non-inertial frame, all points of which are moving in Minkowski space, is certainly flat. This is not correct. The prevailing opinion is often based on arbitrariness of coordinate transformations. Moreover, the geometry is not changed under these transformations; in particular, it is impossible with the help of such transformations to pass from Minkowski space into a space with non-zero curvature. However, a metric tensor under such transformations (together with other space objects) is transformed according to certain rules (§ 83 [16]), specifically

$$g_{ik} = \frac{\partial x'^l}{\partial x^i} \frac{\partial x'^m}{\partial x^k} g'_{lm}$$

All other transformations are not coordinate transformations and they may be called, in particular, *metric tensor's transformations*.

A well-known example is a rotating reference frame. Einstein [13] often used this frame as an

illustrative example of reference frame with Riemannian geometry. Space of rotating reference frame has a non-zero curvature, since the sum of triangle angles in the rotating reference frame is less than two right angles (§ 8.9 [3]). Direct calculation of the curvature tensor⁴ of metric of rotating reference frame (§ 82 [16])

$$ds^2 = [c^2 - \Omega(x^2 + y^2)]dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 + 2\Omega y dx dt - 2\Omega x dy dt$$

proves that such a frame possesses pseudo-Riemann geometry, the Riemann tensor of which contains 16 non-zero terms. Scalar curvature of the frame

$$R = -2\Omega^2 \frac{\Omega(x^2 + y^2)^2 - \Omega^2(x^2 + y^2) - 2c^2}{(\Omega(x^2 + y^2)^2 - \Omega^2(x^2 + y^2) - c^2)^2}$$

S. A. Podosenov [11] found a non-zero curvature tensor, Ricci tensor and scalar curvature for uniformly rotating frame.

A.4 In A.A. Logunov's lectures on the relativity theory [14], the following accelerated frame is considered

$$x = X - \frac{c^2}{g} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{g^2 t^2}{c^2}} - 1 \right], \quad (III)$$

where g is an acceleration. Unduly great importance was attached to this frame. In the author's opinion [14], all points of this frame are moving with the same proper acceleration g , i.e. the frame is an uniformly accelerated reference frame. The same idea is the basis of Bella's task paradoxical solution [15]. An error becomes apparent when we remember that proper time in accelerated frames is a function of coordinates [1, 3, 16], or expression (3) in this article. Then proper accelerations of different points (III) will be different.

However, it is worth to dwell in detail on author's proof of the frame homogeneity (III). In [14], a concept of *form-invariant movement* is introduced, in which the view of metric doesn't change with the spatial translation. It is claimed that the metric of frame (I)

$$ds^2 = \frac{c^2 dt^2}{1 + \frac{g^2 t^2}{c^2}} - \frac{2g dt dx}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{g^2 t^2}{c^2}}} - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 \quad (IV)$$

is form-invariant. The proof of this assertion is based on the fact that the metric tensor (IV) does not depend on the spatial coordinates. Actually, this assertion is incorrect for the non-diagonal metric tensor. Frame (IV) is not orthogonal, and translation on one of the coordinates is accompanied by the conversion of other coordinates. Conversion of time $\hat{t} = t/(1 + g^2 t^2/c^2)$ leads the metric (IV) to the metric

$$ds^2 = c^2 d\hat{t}^2 - 2g d\hat{t} dx - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2,$$

which does not distinguish from the metric (IV) in the limit of small speeds. Further conversion (§ 8.14 [3])

$$t' = \hat{t} \exp[-g(x + (g\hat{t}^2)/2)/c^2]; \quad x' = x; \quad y' = y; \quad z' = z$$

leads the metric tensor to diagonal type

$$ds^2 = \frac{\exp[-g(x + (g\hat{t}^2)/2)/c^2]}{1 - (g^2 \hat{t}^2)/c^2} c^2 dt'^2 - \left(1 - \frac{g^2 \hat{t}^2}{c^2}\right)^{-1} dx'^2 - dy'^2 - dz'^2.$$

Coefficient with the first term is now clearly depends on the position in space. Therefore, the proof of metric (IV) form-invariant is untenable.

⁴ Calculations were made with the help of the analytical calculation frame *Maple*.